

**MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE
TEACHING METHODOLOGY**

Kuandikova Venera Amangeldievna

Chimboy district of the Republic of Karakalpakstan

31 – school English teacher

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7956754>

Abstract

talks about the use of modern pedagogical technologies in the study of foreign language teaching methods , the study of the possibilities of using different technologies in the course of the lesson.

Key words: pedagogy, education, method, young generation, innovation.

INTRODUCTION

It is known that learning and teaching foreign languages is all developed and developing countries, it is also time in our homeland – Karakalpakstan a requirement. For young people to learn foreign languages, and everything else the conditions created for our compatriots have a positive result proving. Not only in the case of foreign languages, but serious changes and updates in all aspects of the world of science implemented. Of course, at the beginning of such a huge creative work by our head of state, attention to the youth, to the future trust. In today's conditions, highly qualified personnel in preparation, modern systems of teaching and modern pedagogy it is desirable to implement it on the basis of technologies. Advanced, modern pedagogical technologies is that it is placed in it a learning process that guarantees the achievement of goals is planned and as a result . Indeed, the lessons are successful the organization is the correct design, organization of the educational process and its implementation.

Innovative pedagogy is a new direction of educational development in the present period caused. Innovative means "introduction (dissemination) of innovation" in English. The socio-psychological aspect of innovation in America developed by researcher E. Rodgers. It is an innovation process of participants , their attitude to the news, etc. The concepts of novelty and innovation are mutually different in scientific areas. "Innovation" means a tool, a new method, methodology, technology. "Innovation" is a process that develops according to certain stages of education. The development of world science is growing and developing day by day. It was this positive development that affected our country as well. Advanced innovative technologies are being applied to our world of science. It would not be wrong to say that the wide application of

advanced, modern innovative technologies in the fields of education has opened the door to many opportunities and goals for young people learning foreign languages.

Language learning is one of the most important areas in human society. Language, which is a means of communication, can be acquired practically in a natural environment, i.e. in the family, in the community or in an organized manner. Knowledge of language phenomena is taught theoretically. Knowledge of languages, especially multilingualism, is of great importance in our time of increased international relations. Pupils and students studying in our country usually study three languages. These languages are referred to by special names. These are: mother tongue, second language, and foreign language. The mother tongue is the first language that plays a special role in the formation of thinking. When talking about the second language, it is considered as the language of brothers and neighbors of other nationalities. A foreign language is the language of a foreign country. In our republic, Western Europe (English, Spanish, German, French) and Eastern (Arabic, Turkish, Persian, Chinese, Indian) languages taught. These languages are part of the curricula of educational institutions received. The process of teaching all three languages is different. Mother tongue and second language a natural situation, and a foreign language is learned in an artificial environment. Communication in a foreign language, mainly, it takes place in the lesson under the guidance of the teacher. A foreign language among three languages learning and teaching differ sharply in certain aspects. And this is his in turn, requires the use of appropriate foreign language teaching technology. Language teacher of the student through thorough assimilation of the achievements of methodological science accumulated language experience and further it improvement . His method of effective teaching of foreign languages requires knowing. Learning and teaching foreign languages is a foreign language in many ways to develop the issues of teaching methodology from the theoretical side and of theory in practice. Therefore, a foreign language A person who is committed to learning and teaching it to others in the future language teaching methodology. The subject of the methodology is education through the subject of a foreign language process and methods, foreign language teaching science, teacher and student activities learning methodology.

The main concepts of methodology - method, method, principle. Didactics – what shall we teach? is the content of teaching. Methodology - how do we teach? Education methods and methods. Method - the concept of methodology is derived from the Greek-Latin word "methodos-"methodus" and means ways,

methods leading to a certain goal. The narrow and broad meaning of the term can be found in various literature. The term "methodology" in a narrow sense means the concept related to the concrete lesson process of education. Interpreted as a guided learning process that includes instruction related to lesson planning and preparation of instructional materials. The term "method" broadly refers to the selection, classification and distribution of teaching material.

It is a process of personality formation by getting to know the educational resources and values of a foreign culture and applying them to one's own cultural life. In Europe, the study of foreign languages has long been considered a privilege in higher education, and public schools are seen as educating the privileged few.

The methodology of foreign language teaching as a science has more than 200 years of history. During this period, it can be observed that different attitudes towards foreign language teaching methodology were expressed. One of these views belongs to academic L V Shcherbais considered In his opinion, the methodology of teaching any subject should be a science however , it is not considered a theoretical science. It solves practical problems. In particular, the methodology of foreign language teaching does not rely only on the evidence of psychology, but is based on general and specific linguistic studies. If linguistics deals with the origin and laws of movement of language phenomena, the methodology answers the question of what should be done in order to use the necessary language phenomenon in practice based on these laws. The most valuable books on methodology are also written by linguists. These include G. Suit, one of the 19th century phoneticians and a great English linguist, O. Yesperson, who is considered the most original phonetician and theoretical linguist in England at the end of the 19th and early 20th centuries, and one of the most prominent French linguists in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, F. .Bryuns and Brealya, prominent anglicist and famous phonetician V. Fyotor and others. Academician L V Shcherba and his mentor, the great linguist I A Boduinde-Courtone and their students dealt with the issue of language teaching methodology in Russia. Psychologists have a different attitude to the methodology of foreign language teaching . Professor V.A. Artemov made a valuable comment about the relationship between methodology and psychology. In his opinion, psychology provides material for methodology. Methodology studies how the teacher conducts the lesson. Psychology deals with how students learn this subject. However, I cannot fully agree with this opinion.

Because the teacher in the process of teaching, and the student in the period of mastering, experience certain mental processes and states, whether they want to or not, they face and are influenced by the laws of psychology.

A deeper study of the literature on the history of methodology shows that some researchers call methodology an art. They usually refer to the idea of the French Methodist Penlache, that there are no "good" or "bad" methods, there are "good" or "bad" teachers. People who have such an opinion can be answered with the thoughts of the German Methodist E. Otto, expressed in 1924. He says: "If someone considers methodology to be an art, he confuses the theory of science with its practical application." Each discipline has its own set of concepts.

Among the basic concepts adopted in foreign language teaching methodology, the following can be included: educational system, educational method, educational principle, educational tool, methodology.

Foreign language teaching method means a set of teacher and student activities that ensure achievement of practical, general educational, educational and developmental goals of foreign language teaching. The term method is used in the sense of "set of educational methods" and "direction of education". First, in the theory of education, the process is used in the sense of methods, and in the second sense, we can find it in works on the history of teaching methods. For example, translation method, correct method, conscious comparative method, traditional method, intensive method, etc. The phenomena of nature and society are interconnected and develop in a continuous relationship. Since the sciences are reflections of objective reality, none of them exists in isolation from the others. At the same time, the phenomenon and the subject can be a source of research for many sciences, for example, linguistics (linguistics), psychology (psychology), pedagogy (didactics) study the social phenomenon "language" from their own point of view. The term "foreign language methodology" evokes a "connection" in the mind of a person as follows: first of all, a set of methods and methodical methods aimed at teaching a language is understood, or scientific knowledge about teaching methods, and finally, an independent pedagogical science comes before our eyes. The methodology of foreign language teaching has developed in harmony with didactics. It is undoubtedly known to all of us that the teaching theories of all educational subjects are based on didactics science and receive scientific nutrition from it. Foreign language teaching is also based on didactics. Didactics is the general theory of education, methodology is the science of teaching a specific subject, linguodidactics is the

general theory of language teaching, and linguomethodology is the science of teaching a specific language.

Conclusions

is a multifaceted teaching , and in this process a person experiences complex psychological changes. In particular, the process of comparing the native language with a foreign language occurs. Different teaching methods and technologies are used in this process. With the help of modern pedagogical technologies, teaching by comparing the foreign language with the mother tongue gives an effective result. Teaching a foreign language requires knowledge of its methodology. Methodology and technologies are important in the process of learning a foreign language. There are various methods of teaching methodology.

Practice is the best way to master all knowledge. The exercise gives a positive result not only in foreign language education, but also in mastering knowledge in all fields. The effective organization of the lesson, the role of the pedagogue and modern pedagogical technologies in it is incomparable. To organize the process of learning a foreign language with a communicative approach, to bring the next level to the level of intercultural communication, to achieve such results and it is important to pay attention to the last step, "exercise technology". In order to effectively organize the foreign language teaching process, it is necessary to acquire knowledge of modern pedagogical information and communication technologies.

References:

1. Jalolov J. Foreign language teaching methodology.- Tashkent . "Teacher Publishing House" 1996.
2. Saydaliev S. Essays on foreign language teaching methodology. -Namangan.-2004 .
3. Gerhard Neuner und Hans Hunfeld Methoden des fremdsprachlichen Deutschunterrichts.- Berlin , Muenchen. Langenscheidt 1997
4. Yoldoshev J. Problems of new didagogical technologies directions.- Public education in 1999.
5. Kleppin, K. Fehler und Fehlerkorrektur.-Berlin Munchen. Langenscheidt 2002.
6. Rogova G.B., Rabinovich F.M., Sakharova T.E. Methodology of foreign language learning in middle school. - M.: Prosveshchenie, 2001.

7. Issues of modern technology of teaching foreign languages. Proceedings of the republican scientific and practical conference.- Tashkent 2007 .

Internet sites

8. <http://www.ziyonet.uz>.

9. <http://www.pedagog.uz>.

